

A Vision On The Board Of Avoidance And Settlement Of Disputes As One Of The Means Of Settling Disputes In Fidic Contracts

Amal Boulghab

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 16, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : FIDIC,Council,Disagreements, Dispute</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5112345</p>	<p><i>FIDIC contract is considered one of the interesting contracts in the construction sector, especially because of its distinguished means of settling disputes, which made it attractive models for investment. The most important of these means is the Dispute Resolution and Avoidance Council, which is the modified version in the second edition 2017 of FIDIC for the former Dispute Resolution Council, where the work of tribal settlement of the claim was added before it turned into a dispute presented to the Council</i></p> <p><i>In the foregoing, going directly to the council without trying to avoid conflict and without activating the role of consultations carried out by the engineer before resorting to raising the claim before the council. The golden rules of FIDIC are also necessary for any project dealing with the framework of FIDIC, so that if any country relies on a unified system of FIDIC or on the FIDIC model with its golden rules, it implicitly finds itself obligated to implement the provisions of FIDIC.</i></p>

Introduction

The construction sector in all countries is considered one of the most important topics that are witnessing successive developments and modifications in order to reach a high degree of quality, whether in the private or public sectors. In order to attract foreign investment and facilitate its strong attraction to the contracting sector, many countries have resorted to adopting model contracts such as FIDIC. Jordan is one of the most prominent Arab countries that relied on the FIDIC contract through the unified contract for construction projects, due to its flexibility in procedures for resolving disputes by amicable means without resorting to the judiciary. Especially since this sector is characterized by a large number of claims and disputes in many cases are stressful for both parties.

Whoever establishes his projects based on the FIDIC contract finds him in front of the means of resolving disputes stipulated in these model contracts as alternative ways of resorting to the judiciary, and the first of these means that is resorted to is the DAAB (1) Board of Dispute Resolution and Avoidance.

And in this research, we will try to address the Council for Avoiding and Resolving Conflicts in the FIDIC 2017 edition, because of its essential additions that did not exist previously mandatory decisions?

Some questions arise from this problem, including:

* How is this council and why?

* What is its legal nature?

How satisfied are the parties with his decisions?

Is it possible to bypass the council and resort to other means to resolve the conflict?

We find that the importance of the research lies in recognizing the role of the Council through its stages of development or successive modifications, since it appeared and abolished the role of the consulting engineer, until it was named the Council for Avoidance and Settlement of Disputes DAAB in FIDIC contracts in its second edition 2017, how to work with it and the most important differences between it and DAB in Edition 2006, after modification. We also highlight the golden rules for the new FIDIC contract. Especially since this type of topic is of interest to legal professionals, engineers and contractors alike, and it is a fertile ground for research, and in it previous studies that shed light on the Dispute Resolution Board and the role of the consulting engineer. In addition to the most important recent studies that dealt with the Council to resolve and avoid disputes, especially in the Arab world, but from different angles.

In order to answer this problem, we relied on each of the comparison of data and materials formulated in many FIDIC models that pertain to the council, in addition to analyzing some differences in the roles entrusted to the council through its stages of development.

Therefore, we decided to divide this work into two sections, where we dedicate the first topic to the nature of the Council and its historical development through the various editions of FIDIC. As for the second topic, we focus on the dispute and how to refer it to the Council and the extent of the mandatory or authoritative decisions of the Council in the presence of the golden rules of FIDIC.

The first topic: the concept of the council for avoiding and settling disputes:

In this topic, we will discuss the definition of the council for avoiding and settling disputes, according to the jurisprudential definitions that were said about it. Then the emergence and historical development of the council and its nature and how to appoint it in the first requirement, then we devote the second requirement to the difference between the council and other alternative means.

The first requirement: the definition of the council for avoiding and settling disputes, and its establishment.

Section one: Defining the council.

The Dispute Avoidance and Settlement Council is considered one of the most important and latest methods that have recently emerged for settling disputes in FIDIC contracts due to its characteristics. For this reason, it is necessary to define this council based on what was stated in the general conditions of the FIDIC second edition 2017, especially since in the first editions it did not address its definition, but only explained its formation as stated in Article (1.1.22) (2). It is necessary to resort to the jurisprudence interpretations previously to define the council, which was derived from Article (20) of the FIDIC contract.

Perhaps the most prominent of these definitions is that it is a form of amicable settlement, as it is entrusted to a third party who has the confidence of the parties called (the Dispute Resolution Board) to receive the disputes arising between the two parties to the contract, to study and consider them in order to reach a solution represented in a decision issued by the Council after its examination and study. And that it is also a field means to look into the dispute, as the disputes are referred to the Council in writing from the time of their occurrence. Inspection and study take place at a time when the evidence for it and the circumstances leading to its occurrence are still apparent (3).

In another definition, it came as a body of consultants with experience, impartial and independent, and that it is often formed before the start of the project, where they meet at the work site periodically, provided that the council members are provided with the contract document, plans, and specifications to be aware of the procedures The project and its participants, so that they remain along with the development and progress of the work. The council also meets with the employer and the contractor during regular visits to the site and alerts them to the necessity of resolving disputes at the work level, but if the two parties are unable to resolve them between themselves, it is referred to the council to take its decision (4).

We find that this definition is somewhat in accordance with considering his work as the work of the guide, although this is not his main function, so that if we follow this definition, it was meant by DAB. Although the council in the 2006 edition did not have any advisory role, but was only entrusted with resolving the conflict, unlike the 2017 edition, in which the name of the council was changed from the Dispute Resolution Council to the Dispute Resolution Council.

Also, this definition linked the council to the commission, which consists of 3 people, although the council can be composed of one person.

These jurisprudential interpretations in defining the council, we find that they were originally derived from the work of the council in itself, and from how it was appointed and how it took the decision stipulated in Article 20 of the general conditions of the red FIDIC contract. Although the FIDIC contract did not set a definition for the council, it gave all the details that if we collected them, we would get a definition of this council.

We have decided that the definition of the Dispute Resolution and Avoidance Council should be as follows: It is the modern form in which the role of the consulting engineer and the Dispute Resolution Council has been compensated as a permanent council whose main work is to avoid conflict. And providing assistance during the project period whenever the parties so request. The parties are not obligated to act on advice given to them by the DAAB. The latter is not bound in any future dispute by the opinions presented during this process. It also works quickly and less costly that arises in connection with the execution of the works or the contract, so that the members of the Board are appointed in a manner It is joint between the employer and the contractor, which consists of one or three qualified members, and whose work is different from the work of the arbitral tribunal.

We derived this definition from how and conditions for appointing the council and how to take its decisions, second edition 2017 of the FIDIC contract.

The second section: the establishment and historical development of the council:

Addressing the emergence and historical development of the Council for Avoidance and Settlement of Disputes, is useful in knowing the importance of the amendments made to it from the beginning of its appearance in the late sixties until its last amendment, as it was modified more than once to suit the nature of construction projects, as follows:

First - The emergence of the council: Dispute resolution councils first appeared in the United States of America in the late sixties, in dams, tunnels, and water management projects, and took the form of a joint advisory council. This council was concerned with resolving disputes that arise during the construction of the Washington border dam. The council's terms of reference were technical, and it settled disputes during the period of the project's establishment and not at its end.

These councils also took the image of the "Dispute Review Board", which was established to resolve the disputes that arise during the construction of the Eisenhower Tunnel project in the state of Colorado in the

United States of America, where it proved successful, as many disputes occurred during the project, which led to the prolongation of the project. As a result, this led to huge material and time losses, knowing that work on this project began in 1968 and ended in 1974 (5).

The task of the Dispute Review Board was limited to merely examining disputes and expressing an advisory opinion on them without issuing enforceable rulings, as its decisions were recommendations that did not have a binding character. Hence, the party against whom it was issued is not obligated to implement what is stated in it. The dispute was also submitted to a higher body for litigation to determine the mandatory capacity through the issuance of a binding judgment.

The use of these councils has increased steadily, and they were used as an alternative to the ordinary litigation system, at the (Pound) Conference in (1976), where senior judges and lawyers pointed out the disadvantages of the ordinary litigation system, which leads to delays, and the increasing expenses that burden the parties in the courts Overcrowded with disputes of all kinds.

Until this date, this method has been applied in the United States of America in (500) projects with a total cost of (60) billion dollars. By conducting a survey of these projects, a small percentage of them are about (20) cases in which the decisions of the Council were objected (6).

With the beginning of the year (1980) the World Bank decided to form a board to review disputes for a major construction contract in Honduras, which is the El Kahun Dam project. The Bank insisted on forming the said board, and linked its approval to finance the project with its formation, in order to avoid disputes arising from misunderstandings between the parties The odds of doing so were high due to the great disparity in their artistic and cultural backgrounds (the owner was from Honduras, the contractor from Italy, the engineer from Switzerland), and thus dispute review boards emerged at the international level.

Second - the development of the board: In 1995, the World Bank issued a document, in which it came for the first time, a recommendation to form boards to review all disputes in projects that are financed by the Bank. Provided that the council consists of only one expert, and this has been a great success.

After the success of the dispute review boards, this led to the adoption of some countries by these boards. In 1996, the United Kingdom issued a law for the settlement of disputes in building and construction contracts through these boards. It stipulated that all construction contracts executed in the United Kingdom should include clauses that decide Formation of councils to settle disputes. Those in charge of the construction industry there found that it is preferable for large projects to include a council consisting of several people instead of a council consisting of only one person.

Referring to the FIDIC contract, we find that it has followed the footsteps of the World Bank. In 1996, FIDIC issued an amendment to Article (67) of the General Conditions of 1987 for contracting mechanical equipment (design and implementation) in order to test it, and then applying it to the rest of the projects if it proves successful. At that specific stage, the dispute settlement councils came into existence in FIDIC contracts, as the Dispute Settlement Council differs from the Dispute Review Board in terms of the first issuing provisions of binding and temporary character, as the Replacing the engineer's role in settling disputes with the Dispute Resolution Board as a result of the criticism leveled at the dual role played by the engineer, and Article (67, paragraph 1) (7) has indicated the mechanism by which the dispute is referred to the engineer and the decision issued by him as follows:

1- The text of Article (67, paragraph 1) related to the engineer's decision: (8)

If a dispute arises, of any kind between the Employer and the Contractor related to the contract or arising out of it or related to or arising out of the execution of the works, whether it arises during the execution of the works or after its completion and whether before or after any denial or other form of termination of the contract, including any dispute related to the opinion or an order, decision, certificate or evaluation by the engineer. The subject of the dispute must be referred first to the engineer in writing, with a copy of this book sent to the other party. It must be indicated in the referral letter that the referral was made pursuant to this article. Provided that the engineer informs the employer and the contractor of his decision within a period not exceeding (48) days following the day of delivering the letter of assignment, and it must be indicated in this decision that it was taken pursuant to this article.

The contractor in each case, unless the contract has ended, shall continue to carry out the works with due diligence, and the contractor and the employer shall implement without delay any decision issued by the engineer unless he has withdrawn from it in an amicable settlement or in an arbitral award. As stipulated below:

If the employer or contractor is not satisfied with any decision of the engineer, or if the engineer does not give notice of his decision on or before the eighty-fourth day following the day of delivery of the letter of assignment. Each of the employer or contractor may, on or before the seventy day following the delivery of the notification of this decision, or on or before the seventy day following the day of the expiry of the said eighty-four day period, at the expense of the circumstances, notify the other party, sending a copy to the engineer for information, of his desire to start Arbitration in accordance with the texts set forth hereinafter regarding the subject matter of the dispute. This notification, which was sent, proves the right to start arbitration in the matter

of the dispute as stipulated hereinafter, and subject to Article (76, paragraph 4), the arbitration procedures in this regard shall not commence until after this notification is given. .

If the engineer gives notice to the employer and the contractor of his decision on the subject matter of the dispute and does not send a notification of his intention to start arbitration regarding this dispute on or before the seventy day following the day on which the two parties received the engineer's notice. The said decision has become final and binding on the employer and contractor.

As for the legal nature of the consulting engineer's decision, there are many jurisprudential opinions about the legal adaptation of the engineer's decision, as some of them see that the task of the consulting engineer is that of the arbitrator. While others see it as a semi-arbiter, it is not obligated to follow arbitration procedures. In our opinion, these two opinions express their support for the role of the consulting engineer within the framework of Article 67 of the FIDIC conditions, while others, including Professor Seppala, view the opinion to which Dr. Mustafa Abdel Mohsen al-Habashi indicated that he is not arbitrary in any way, as the character of impartiality and independence is not available in him being appointed by the parties to the conflict. Therefore, he is their representative, in addition to the fact that the decision issued by him is not final and binding, and the role of the consulting engineer in this case is nothing but a waste of time (9).

For our part, we see that although the consulting engineer speeds up the settlement of the dispute in order to avoid stopping the implementation of projects, this does not always take him away from doubt, and considers him not impartial and inclined in favor of the employer at the expense of the contractor, especially since the employer is appointed by him, and he is the one who can dismiss him and appoint Jealous.

In 1999, FIDIC introduced the idea of the council to the rest of the contracts issued by it. It also modified the idea of having one member and using other members in mega projects. The Asian Development Bank also adopted the idea of the council.

In the year 2000, the World Bank amended the procedures of its dispute review boards, so that its decisions became recommendations of a temporary binding nature, in recognition of the impact of the waning of the arbitral authority of the engineer on the conduct of contractual disputes. In 2004 the World Bank formulated the General Terms of Dispute Resolution Board which are consistent with the FIDIC. In 2002, the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) drafted laws for the Dispute Resolution Board (10).

On 1/6/2004, Jordan adopted the red FIDIC contract in construction projects, including the amendment made by the FIDIC Union regarding the replacement of the role of the consulting engineer in the Dispute Resolution Council, in public works contracts in which the approval of the red FIDIC contract is required, and in the unified contract in which the Jordanian legislator left the freedom For individuals using the red FIDIC contract, provided that the project value is not less than 250 thousand Jordanian dinars (11).

As for the 2006 edition of the FIDIC, it was identical and consistent with the FIDIC (1999), especially Article 20 of it, which included a reference to the Dispute Resolution Board, the conditions that must be met by members and how the board is formed.

As for the second edition of FIDIC 2017, it came with a different idea of how to resolve disputes, which is to change the Dispute Resolution Board (DAB), as we mentioned earlier, to the Dispute Prevention and Resolution Board (DAAB) (12).

This edition introduces a new work for the council to try to help avoid conflict. The idea is that not every claim necessarily leads to a conflict.

It should be noted here that the new FIDIC 2017 version is set for the duration of the project with parties inviting at fixed intervals, not on an ad hoc basis as was the case in the past (DABs).

It also applies to all three contracts (yellow, red, and silver). Whereas in the past, the Permanent Dispute Adjudicating Board known as (DAB) ruled the disputes arising from the Red Book, while the Special Dispute Resolution Board known as (DABs) governed the disputes arising from the Yellow and Silver Books of FIDIC contracts.

The second requirement: the formation of a council to avoid disputes and its legal nature.

Section One: Formation of the Council.

The selection and appointment of board members to avoid and resolve disputes is one of the most important matters related to the work of the board. Therefore, they must be meticulous in their selection of qualified members for the success of the board.

Based on that, Article 21, paragraph 2, of the Red FIDIC contract dealt with the manner in which the Dispute Resolution Board is appointed, as follows:

The Board shall consist either of a single member or of three members, as specified in the contract data, from suitably qualified persons. If there is no limitation of the number, and the two parties do not agree otherwise, the council shall be formed of three members.

The single member or the three members (as the case may be) shall be selected from those persons whose names are listed in the contract data, except for any person who is unable or unwilling to accept appointment to the Board.

If the council will consist of three members, then each team must choose one member to obtain the approval of the other team. The two parties shall consult with both of these members to agree on the third member, who is appointed to be the chairman of the council.

The Council shall be deemed to have completed its formation on the date on which both parties and the single member of the Council, or all three members of the Council (as the case may be), sign the Dispute Prevention and Settlement Council Agreement (13).

Knowing that the FIDIC confirms this by issuing the most important lists of persons nominated and qualified professionally to carry out the task of members of the Dispute Resolution Board (14). This applies to the Board of Avoidance and Settlement of Disputes.

We note here that some of the criticisms directed at the role of the consulting engineer in Article 67 of the FIDIC contract of 1987, with regard to impartiality, were avoided. The Council's work has also been expanded by adding conflict avoidance work.

Section Two: The legal nature of the Dispute Resolution Council.

The introduction of the task of avoiding conflict on the council changed the traditional form of FIDIC dispute resolution, it is neither arbitration nor litigation, and not necessarily enforceable, so the legal adaptation of the council must be addressed. In the beginning, the dispute resolution council is one of the alternative ways to resolve disputes, which means the predominance of the element of voluntary consensus in its composition. This council is established through two parallel agreements:

- The first agreement: It is the same construction contract that is guaranteed by the two parties to the project (the owner and the contractor) as a condition stipulating the formation of a council in which the services of a third party (one or more), independent and neutral, is guaranteed to reach a solution to the disputes that arise between the parties, provided that it provides solutions Quickly and during the implementation of the work and not after completion.
- The second agreement: It is a contract concluded by the parties to the construction contract (the owner and the contractor) with a member or members of this council. It is a contract that stipulates the member's commitment to provide his services to the project parties by assuming the duties of the council's membership. And that in return for a certain amount in return for his fees.

Thus, this council is a contractual establishment, being the result of the joint will of the owner and the contractor on the one hand, and the convergence of the will of these two members on the other hand. There have been many jurisprudential opinions that were said in the legal qualification of the Dispute Resolution Council, as follows: (15).

- First opinion: Those who hold this view believe that the Dispute Resolution Council is an arbitration body, and they attribute this to the fact that the arbitrator's task is to listen to the opinions of both parties. Thus, he checks the facts before him and interprets the contract. And then the law is applied and the behavior of the litigants is evaluated and then a judgment is issued.
- Second Opinion: Those who hold this view say that the council's task in resolving disputes is semi-arbitration, because the council is not obligated to follow arbitration procedures. It is also appointed by the parties and is paid by them. The reason for comparing it to the arbitrator is due to the condition of impartiality and lack of interest in which it is required, and that the decisions issued by the arbitrator have binding and final force for the parties in most cases.
- Third opinion: Those who hold this opinion say that the Dispute Resolution Board (formerly) is a body of independent professional experts that acts according to its skill and discretion. The parties agree to identify a specific expert, as well as the expert to hear the statements of witnesses and parties and their observations that they make in the course of the dispute. The court also takes the expert's opinion as a matter of appeal, without being restricted to adopting it. Thus, it is a simple presumption that can be proven to the contrary, so one of the parties can prove fraud, bad faith or a serious mistake that can be issued by the bad faith of the Council.

We find here that the first and second opinions focused on the role of the arbitrator and not on the role of the council, because by referring to the rules of the FIDIC, we find that the role of the council according to the second edition of 2017 has become dependent on providing assistance and discussing informally in an attempt to decide on any issue or difference that may arise between them during contract execution. As for his decision, if the parties agree to it, it may become binding and final. Or in the event of no notification after consent within 28 days of receiving the council's decision, it also becomes final and binding. In the event of a notice of dissatisfaction with certain items, the decision remains final and binding with regard to the items in which no notice of non-acceptance was issued, and this is what is stipulated in Articles (21.4.3) and (21.4.4) (16).

The second topic: Procedures for submitting a dispute to the Dispute Resolution Council and issuing its decisions.

It is necessary to know the mechanism by which the dispute is referred to the Dispute Avoidance and Resolution Board. In order to find out the adequacy of the legal regulation in the manner in which the dispute is referred to the Council. Thus, knowing the effectiveness of the procedures drawn up by the FIDIC in its 2017 edition to resolve the conflict, and this is what we discuss in the first requirement.

In addition to the decisions he issues and the extent to which they are mandatory, and this is what we allocate in the second requirement.

The first requirement: refer the dispute to the Dispute Resolution Council.

In order to know how the dispute is referred to the council, it was necessary to know what the dispute is referred to the council. Therefore, this requirement will be studied as follows:

In the first section we deal with the definition of the dispute and the dispute agreement, and in the second section we deal with how to refer the dispute to the Dispute Resolution Board.

Section One: Definition of Dispute and Dispute Agreement.

First- Definition of Dispute: In the previous edition of 2006, it was very necessary to have a dispute to be before the Dispute Resolution Board (DAB), where there is no effect for the Council unless there is a dispute, unlike the DAAB, which begins its impact and work even without a dispute as one of its first goals is to facilitate the process avoid conflicts that may arise between the parties. However, conflict must be defined, which is the sure direction in the event that it is not reached to avoid it. Dispute linguistically is the plural of a dispute or a dispute, and they are litigation, and it is said that it is disputed in such a dispute and a dispute, i.e. quarreling with it, as well as the disputation of a dispute that attracts it in litigation. And between them there is a conflict of any dispute over a right, and a contentious dispute (17).

As for the International Court of Justice, the dispute is defined as a disagreement on a matter of law or reality, any conflict between legal views or interests between two persons. It can also be defined as any situation that calls for a claim by one party to the other party, with the result that the other party rejects it in whole or in part, which requires prompt and effective treatment. Thus, it is referred to the Dispute Resolution Board or Arbitration, as the case may be. Note that the word "dispute" can be used to refer to every dispute arising from the relationship between the employer and the contractor, through which one of the parties requests the other party to comply with its obligation or demand amounts due (18).

According to construction contracts, the word dispute is a request by an aggrieved party (or who is believed to be harmed) to obtain what he considers to have a right to compensate for the damage he has suffered, or that he believes that he has a right to it based on a condition in the contract, or because of a breach Or the breach by the other party of the contract, or for a reason related to the law governing the contract (19). The dispute may be purely national in that it does not involve a foreign element, as if all its elements and conditions required by the contract, such as the place, people and reason, are internal, and therefore the rules of internal law apply to it, for example, if we take Jordanian law, the rules related to the unified contract issued by the Ministry of Public Works and Housing referred to previously are applied. . Here, we find that in the case of applying the internal rules to internal construction contracts, we find that the Jordanian law is optimal compared to the Saudi system, which did not adopt a unified FIDIC contract, commensurate with the orientation of the system within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia because it depends on a copy of the FIDIC contract with a change of some materials that are compatible with the internal situation of the Kingdom Jordanian.

In addition, this dispute may arise from the engineer's tort responsibility that the contractor may institute against him on the grounds that he is from a third party and has no contractual relationship with him, so the basis for his claim is the error of negligence, except that the contract (FIDIC) and the duties imposed on the engineer have It is easy for him to prove these duties (20). In addition, the damage must be available, so it should be inflicted on the contractor or third parties, whatever harm is, provided that it is real, direct, and legitimate, meaning that the attack takes place on the legitimate interest of the injured party. It also requires the existence of a causal relationship between them, as the foreign engineer can deny his responsibility by denying the causal relationship between the error and the damage, such as proving the foreign cause (force majeure, sudden accident, the act of the injured himself or the act of others).

Also, the engineer's tort responsibility does not depend on the mere occurrence of a mistake made by him in the course of his engineering activities, but goes beyond that to include the wrong practices of his subordinates as well. A dependency is required between them, and the damage is caused by the fault of the follower when performing the function or its cause.

Examples of disputes that can be referred to the Board include the following:

A- That the contractor (A) demands the employer (B) that the latter pay him his monthly financial dues for the works completed, or that (A) does not build pictures around the construction contrary to the contract, so he asks (B) to build these pictures, or build (A) The fence in violation of the specifications, so he is asked (b) to demolish the fence and rebuild it according to the provisions of the contract.

B - The dispute may relate to the interpretation of the contracts clause. For example, it states in the contract that a good performance guarantee must be presented by the contractor in favor of the employer without indicating whether the guarantee is a bank or otherwise. At the time the contractor submits a personal guarantee from a full guarantor, the employer disputes this, demanding a bank or cash guarantee.

Since the red FIDIC contract is not a contract of compliance, the council must interpret the contract according to what it included and in a manner consistent with what is required by good faith. Also, the contract is not limited to obligating the contracting party to what is stated in it, but also deals with what is required of it in accordance

with the law, custom and the nature of the disposition, and thus the council can benefit from it to complete the contract. The same is the case when there is a conflict between the rules of the Red FIDIC in the interpretation of the contract and the general legislative rules for the interpretation of the contract.

Second- Dispute Agreement: We mean the Dispute Avoidance and Settlement Council Agreement (DAAB Agreement) as stated in Article (1.1.23) of the general conditions of the red FIDIC contract version 2017, where it is signed (or considered as having been signed) by the two contracting teams, And the individual member or each of the three members of the Council, as the case may be. According to Article (21.1) or Article (21.2) of the general condition of the Red Books 2017, in the event of failure to be appointed, it includes, as a reference, the general terms of the Agreement to Avoid and Settlement of Disputes as contained in the annex to the general conditions, and any amendments that may be agreed upon.

Section Two: How to refer disputes to the Dispute Resolution Board.

A claim may arise:

a- If the Employer considers himself entitled to any additional payment from the Contractor (or a reduction in the contract value) and/or an extension of the defect notification period,

b- If the Contractor considers himself to be entitled to any additional payment from the Employer and/or for an extension of the completion period, or

C- If any party considers itself entitled to any other entitlement or compensation to the other party. Such other entitlement or compensation may be of any kind whatsoever (including in connection with any certification, determination, instruction, notice, opinion or evaluation of the Engineer) except to the extent that it is comprehensive of any entitlement referred to in paragraphs "a" and/or "b" above.

In the event of a claim under paragraphs A or B above, Article (20.2) shall apply.

In the case of a claim under Paragraph (c) above, and when the other party or the engineer rejects the entitlement or the requested compensation, (or considers that it has rejected, if not responded within a reasonable period), it shall not be considered that the claim has turned into a dispute. However, the claimant party, by sending a notification, shall refer the claim to the engineer so that Article (3.7) is applied in this regard. This notification must be sent as soon as practicable, after the claimant party becomes aware of the rejection of the claim (or considered rejected), and attaches the details of the claimant party's case, and the other party or engineer has rejected it (or considered it rejected).

Then, the two parties may agree to avoid conflict, and this is the essential difference between FIDIC 2006 and FIDIC 2017. They may jointly submit a request to the Council (in writing, and with a copy sent to the engineer) to provide assistance and/or to discuss informally, in an attempt to resolve any issue or difference that may arise between them during the execution of the contract. If the council becomes aware of an issue or disagreement, it may invite the two parties to submit such a joint request.

Such a joint application may be submitted at any time, except during the period during which the engineer is performing his duties under Article (3.7) on the subject or the issue on which the dispute is subject, unless the two parties agree otherwise.

This informal assistance is not permanently binding on the parties, as they can then go to raise the dispute before the Council to avoid and resolve disputes formally, where the dispute is referred to the Council according to Article (21.4.1) must:

A- In the event that Article (3.7) applies to the subject of the dispute, the referral shall be made within (42) days from the date of sending or receiving (as the case may be) a notification of dissatisfaction with the engineer's determinations under Article (3.7.5). If the dispute is not referred to the Council within this 42-day period, such notification of dissatisfaction shall be deemed to have lapsed and is no longer valid.

(b) to indicate in the referral that it is made under this Article,

c- The referral presents the point of view of the party referring the case related to the dispute,

d- The assignment shall be in writing, with copies of it being sent to the other party and the engineer, and

e- For a council consisting of three members, the council considers that it has received the letter of referral on the date on which the council chairman receives that referral.

Referral of any dispute to the Board under this Article, unless prohibited by law, shall be deemed to suspend the application of any applicable legislation regarding the period of lapse or limitation.

What is worth noting on this point is that it is implicitly assumed that the council does not act as an arbitral body. This expressly indicates that the resolution of disputes by the Council does not amount to being considered arbitration or an arbitration clause. According to the concept of the Arbitration Law, and therefore, the procedures and decisions of the Council do not apply to the arbitration procedures and provisions, and in cases of contract termination contained in its terms, Articles (15) related to the termination of the contract by the employer, and (16) related to the suspension of work and termination of the contract by the contractor, (18) relating to exceptional events; The dispute resolution clause may lapse, but the arbitration clause does not.

The second requirement: the decisions of the Council to avoid and settle disputes.

The decisions issued by the Council are one of the most important topics in the Dispute Resolution Council, so the decision must be reasoned, through which it is possible to know the extent of the authenticity written by the

decision issued by the Council, and therefore whether it is binding on its parties or not, and this is what will be addressed in this request.

Section one: Reasoning for the decision issued by the Council.

One of the most important conditions that must be met in the decision is that it be in writing (it is a means of proving the council's decision, as well as writing has double importance, on the one hand, it dates the date of the engineer's issuance of his decision so that it can calculate the period required to refer the dispute to arbitration during it, and on the other hand it facilitates The task of arbitration as it allows it to stand on the decision of the entire council (21). It also requires the decision to be reasoned. As the International Federation of Consulting Engineers believes that the reasoning of the decision makes it more acceptable to the parties to the conflict, as the reasons mentioned in the decision indicate that the council has taken note of all aspects of the dispute, and then issued the decision after considering it. In addition, the good reasoning for the council's decision makes the arbitral tribunal, to which the dispute may be presented later, more inclined to support this decision, especially since the council members' visit to the work sites makes them better able to examine the circumstances and circumstances that led to the emergence of the dispute, and thus the council can base its decision on realistic foundations. This reasoning should not conflict with the content of the contract (22).

The second subsection: the authority of the council's decision and its connection with the golden rules of the FIDIC.

The question that arises at this point is whether the decision, once issued, is final and binding on the parties to the conflict? Both parties shall promptly provide to the Board all information, access to the Site, and appropriate facilities, as the Board may require for the purposes of making a decision on the dispute.

Unless the contract has already been abandoned or terminated, the parties shall continue to perform their obligations under the contract.

Therefore, the council must complete its decision and issue it within:

- (a) A period of (84) days after receiving the referral of the dispute, or
- b- That period, as suggested by the council and approved by both parties.

However, if no bill(s) has been paid to the members of the Council at the end of such specified period(s), the Council is not obligated to issue its decision until such outstanding bill(s) is paid in full. In this case, the Board shall issue its decision as soon as practicable after the completion of the payment.

The decision issued in writing must be delivered to both parties (with a copy of it being sent to the engineer), provided that the decision is justified, and that it is indicated that it is issued in accordance with this "Article" (23).

The decision is binding on both parties and they must abide by it - without delay - regardless of whether one of the parties issues a "Notice of Dissatisfaction" with respect to that decision under this "Article". The employer shall be responsible for the engineer's compliance with the council's decision.

If the decision includes one of the two parties to pay a certain amount to the other party, then:

- (1) Subject to paragraph (2) below, such sum shall be deemed immediately due and payable without the need for any approval or notification, and
- 2- The Board may (as part of the award) upon the request of one of the parties, but only if the Board has reasonable grounds to believe that the party paid to it will be unable to return the amount (in the event of an arbitral award reversing the payment under Article 21.6-), To request the paying party to provide an appropriate guarantee against this amount (based on the sole discretion of the Board).

The actions of the Council should not be considered as arbitration, and the members of the Council should not act as arbitrators.

The same is the case if the parties agree to give the council the authority to issue advisory opinions whose role is limited to advising the parties on some issues of unclear dimensions to them, in order to have a non-binding character for both parties. Such an advisory opinion is usually requested when the parties need some assistance in interpreting some vague contractual clauses that impede efforts to resolve the dispute. When referring the issue of interpretation to the Council, its task is usually limited to the basis of contractual documents only, without any other means (24).

But from our side, we see that this point is often excluded because in our view, once the parties agreed to the contract agreement through the FIDIC model contract, the most attractive point in the FIDIC 2017 model is the new role that the Council enjoys, by facilitating the avoidance of conflict at all stages of the project.

And after we knew that this type of decision is authoritative and obligatory on the parties, the question arises for the owners of some projects that adopt the FIDIC model and despite that do not comply with the rules of FIDIC, especially since the golden rules of FIDIC have been issued, which are protected by intellectual property, so that violating these rules is tantamount to violating the FIDIC model FIDIC.

These golden rules are as follows (25):

- 1- Responsibilities: revolve around the responsibility and roles of the parties and all those mentioned in the contract do not change radically and appoint an engineer with appropriate and sufficient powers to carry out his role (26).

- 2- Clear and unambiguous wording
- 3- Fair and balanced identification of risks
- 4- Giving each party reasonable time to carry out its responsibilities and obtain its rights
- 5- Mandatory referral of disputes to the Dispute Resolution Board to obtain a temporary binding decision as a condition before going to arbitration or the judiciary.

Based on the fifth golden condition of the FIDIC, we find some projects in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia that did not comply with this condition.

The lack of recourse to the council may be due to two reasons: * either because a unified contract in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia was not approved.

*Or, according to Dr. Nabil Abbas, the government agencies did not accept the idea of the Dispute Resolution Council (27).

We prefer the second idea proposed by Dr. Nabil Abbas because it is related to the first idea, as if the government had approved a unified contracting contract based on the FIDIC model, it would have been implicitly authorized to deal with the Council.

Unlike the Kingdom of Jordan, as it adopted the unified contracting contract in 2010 and was amended in 2013, it implicitly acknowledges resorting to the former Dispute Resolution Board and the present Dispute Resolution and Avoidance Council. Many of the projects in which a dispute occurred directly resorted to the Council and were decided upon, and most of their decisions were final and were complied with without resorting to amicable settlement or arbitration (a sample appendix of the decision of the Dispute Resolution Council in Jordan)

Subchapter III: Dissatisfaction with the decision of the Board of Conflict Avoidance and Resolution.

If neither of the two parties is satisfied with the council's decision, then:

A- This party may send a "notification of dissatisfaction" to the other party, along with sending copies of the notification to the council and to the engineer.

b- This notification must state that it is a "notification of dissatisfaction with the council's decision," and that the matter in dispute and the reasons for dissatisfaction should be stated in it.

C- Notifications of dissatisfaction must be issued within (28) days after receiving the council's decision.

If the council fails to issue its decision within this period specified in Article (21.4.3), then any party may, within (28) days after the expiry of this period, send a notification of dissatisfaction to the other party in accordance with the provisions of paragraphs "a" and "b" above.

Except for what is stipulated in the last paragraph of Article 3.7.5 related to dissatisfaction with the engineer's determinations, Article (21.7) regarding failure to comply with the Council's decision, and Article (21.8) in the absence of the Council, no party has the right to initiate arbitration in a dispute, unless he has been issued a "notice of dissatisfaction" with respect to that dispute

If the Council issues its decision on a disputed matter to both parties, and neither of them sends a notification of dissatisfaction under Article (21.4.4) within (28) days after they receive the Council's decision, then the decision becomes final and binding on both parties.

But if the dissatisfied party is not satisfied with part or parts of the decision (only), then:

1- That part(s) must be clearly stated in the notice of dissatisfaction,

2- This part(s) and any other parts of the decision that are affected by this part(s), or that they rely on this part(s) to complete, are deemed to be independent of the rest of the decision, and

3- The rest of the decision is deemed to have become final and binding on both parties, as if a notice of dissatisfaction with it had not been sent.

Thus, as we mentioned previously, in all cases, if there is a dispute, it must first pass to the council. If one of the above-mentioned reasons is not complied with, then it can go to settlement or arbitration according to the terms and periods in force.

Conclusion

The amendments made by FIDIC in its second edition, 2017, are of importance, as they touched on many points, the most important of which is changing the work of the first settlement instrument in the FIDIC contract from the Dispute Resolution Board to the Dispute Resolution Board. By adding the conflict avoidance process, it facilitates tracking the project and finding out everything that would lead to future conflicts being amplified, and it makes the council effective from its inception, unlike the previous model. In addition, this council has become a decision for each of the red, yellow and silver books for FIDIC contracts. Instead of red only, and by referring to the golden rules of the FIDIC, we find that they are essential rules, as deviating from them is considered deviating from the framework of dealing with the FIDIC contract.

-Although some Arab countries such as Saudi Arabia contract many projects by FIDIC model without following the golden rules.

Unlike the Kingdom of Jordan, as it has experience in this field, especially in committing to resolving disputes related to FIDIC, initially through the Dispute Resolution Avoidance Board (example in the appendix).

Although the decisions of this council are mandatory, they remain mandatory dependent on the compliance of the parties, but in the event of objection, the decision is issued binding while waiting for the possibility that one of its parties will not accept the decision issued by the council.

Therefore, we may wait in the next amendments to the FIDIC contract, which also include an improvement in the provisions related to settlement, and an emphasis on the dealers using the FIDIC model to comply with its rules.

Research results:

- We find that the role of the engineer has been reduced in the 1999 edition of FIDIC and the 2006 edition of FIDIC from what it was in the 1987 edition, which gave the consulting engineer a major role in terms of claim management, which sometimes results in the engineer's bias towards the employer who appointed him in the first place.
- We find that the second edition of FIDIC for the year 2017 added an important task for the consulting engineer, which is the need to consult with the parties to the conflict before resorting to the Board of Avoidance and Settlement of Disputes. This task is not completely included in the procedures for avoiding and settling disputes before the council, where if no result is reached by the parties themselves, the claim will be submitted to the council for avoiding and settling disputes.
- Giving an important role to the Council for Avoiding and Resolving Disputes 2017 is very similar to the role of the engineer earlier
- Not placing mandatory clauses in the model contract for the parties to follow the means of resolving the dispute in order with the obligation to resort to the Council to avoid and resolve disputes first. As we find that if the parties do not raise the claim before the Council, they may refer the claim to arbitration.
- Not reaching a sense of the obligation of the council's decision to avoid and settle disputes, as is the case in arbitration.

Therefore, we suggest some recommendations, including:

- * Including the golden rules in the model contract agreements between the parties, so that the parties can see them, because the more model contracts they are clear from the beginning, the less they fall into disputes.
- * Giving an official and mandatory nature to the golden rules in the FIDIC contract, in order to avoid transgressing and canceling them by the parties, especially if they depend on the FIDIC contract form, which the International Federation of Consulting Engineers tries to maintain as much as possible.
- * The agreement between the contract parties to abide by what was stated in the model contracts in terms of arranging resorting to the means of resolving the dispute, beginning with the Council for Avoiding and Resolving Disputes, then amicable means, then arbitration
- * Include the FIDIC model contract articles that oblige the person dealing with these contracts to follow the order of the means of resolving the dispute as stated in the model contract, along with enclosing them with penal terms.

References:

- The Red Book - Special Conditions - Conditions of the construction contract, second edition 2017, FIDIC.
- Daoud Khalaf, A guide to using the construction contract (FIDIC 1999) Perceptions and Applications. 1st floor, Cooperative Press Workers Association, Amman, 2002.
- Daoud Khalaf, Dispute Resolution and Friendly Settlement Council. 1st floor, Cooperative Press Workers Association, Amman, 2002.
- Consolidated contracting for construction projects, website of the Ministry of Public Works and Housing, Jordan, Government Tenders Department, www.gtd.gov.jo
- Mustafa Abdel Mohsen Al-Habashi, Financial balance in international construction contracts - a study of how to achieve financial balance in these contracts - a comparative study. Legal Books House, Egypt, 2008.
- Fayhaa Al-Khalidi, Kuwaiti Lawyer Network, www.lawyerkuwait.com
- Mashaal Abdul Aziz Al-Hajri, the impact of the emergence of dispute settlement councils on the erosion of the semi-arbitration role of the consulting engineer in the FIDIC contract for civil engineering works. Working paper presented to the Faculty of Law conference on the private sector in development, Kuwait, 2005.
- Al-Shalakany Office for Legal Consultations and Advocacy, 1993, Arabic translation of the fourth edition of the FIDIC contract, 2nd edition, Cairo, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Masryah.
- Nabil Abbas et al, terms of construction contract - International Federation of Consulting Engineers - FIDIC. Second Edition, 2017.
- Nabil Abbas, FIDIC Golden Rules.FCI Arb-MAcostE - AIA www.nabilabbas.com
- Wajdi Al-Qurashi, https://www.aleqt.com/2009/02/17/article_196932.html, entry date 9/20/2020

Author Information

Dr. Amal Boulghab

Assistant Professor of Commercial Law

Faculty of Law, Alasala colleges _

Dammam- Saudi Arabia

Email: Amal.bolgab@alasala.edu.sa
